
❄️ FACILITATION GUIDE ❄️

SURPRISES & DREAMS WORKSHOP

→ INTRODUCTION

This is a guide for facilitating future-oriented workshops¹ in order to gather insight for research and support long term planning in nature-based livelihoods².

Developing more narratives around Arctic futures can help local communities, policy makers, and other actors anticipate plausible developments/surprises, understand ongoing dynamics, and aid in decision making. This workshop is designed to help articulate and develop the following aspects of scenario work:

PART I Systems understanding of past, present, and future dynamics

PART II Response and adaptation to plausible surprises that may unfold

PART III Desirable futures for stakeholders and decision makers to strive toward

Time estimates given in this document are only suggestions. Depending on the particular needs of each project and the nature of its inquiry, each part of the workshop can be amplified or de-emphasized. For instance, Part III focuses on imagination and backcasting, articulating actionable steps towards various preferred futures. This can work as a brief closure to Parts I and II, or modified to be the main workshop focus by adding more detailed prompts and designating more time at each step.

→ PREP & PRACTICALITIES

Scheduling Consider “piggybacking” the workshop on another event to streamline participation. If not, consider a neutral time and location that is convenient for most participants.

Invitations Extend invitations and advertise the event with enough time in advance. Require easy registration in order to prepare resources accordingly. It’s

¹ This guide has evolved out of a workshop originally developed by University of Lapland’s Arctic Centre researchers in projects [CHARTER](#), [POVAUS](#), [CLIMINI](#), and [POMURI](#) with colleagues from the Finnish Natural Resources Centre LUKE and Lapland University of Applied Sciences. For a comprehensive list of project acknowledgements, visit the project [Zenodo page](#). A report on the [2022 Inari Workshop](#) is available on the CHARTER website.

² This guide uses examples specific to the reindeer husbandry system, but with some straightforward adjustments this method will also work for other communities and livelihoods.

important to express why the event is important and what might be valuable for participants.

- Space** Book a room in advance and provide plenty of food and drink. The area should be spacious enough for several lively group discussions to occur simultaneously, and tables should comfortably seat a group of 5–8.
- Grouping** Participants should be divided between tables in a way that allows for diverse and productive conversation. It can be helpful to consult with a local expert who understands the social dynamics and skillsets.
- Team** There should be one *general facilitator*, who should be in charge of opening and closing the event, keeping time, presenting slides, and energetically guiding the agenda. For every table, there should be one *chairperson* in charge of guiding the conversations and shepherding their group through the exercises. Every table may also have one *notetaker* who focuses on transcribing insights throughout the workshop, keeping track of who says what; this role may be more or less necessary depending on whether discussions are recorded (see **Permission**). At least one person should be a *photographer*, but whether this is a dedicated role or a shared task is up to the team's discretion.
- Rehearsal** If time allows, it can be very helpful for the organizers to meet in the space beforehand and run through the parts of the workshop.
- Tech** It can be useful to have at least one microphone for the general facilitator, depending on the size of the event. Consider wifi availability and the setup necessary for possible slideshow presentations. Overall, this can be a low-tech workshop run successfully with just paper, pen, and cards.
- Materials** Consider preparing name tags. It can be helpful to print copies of [ground rules for a constructive discussion](#)³ and these facilitation guidelines per table. Each participant should have a pen and piece of paper. At each table, there should be a large sheet of paper to cover the surface, two marker pens in different colors (preferably consistent across tables), a deck of workshop-specific cards⁴, and stickers. Stickers should include a few different colors to mark different issues. When stickers are needed to mark different rounds of selection (see **Part I, Step 2**), they should fit easily on a card and be removable later without damaging the surface.

³ The Timeout Foundation has developed this support tool for facilitated discussions. Access the printout and find more information online: timeoutdialogue.fi/tool/ground-rules-for-a-constructive-discussion

⁴ If you don't have access to the professionally printed deck specific to reindeer husbandry, you can find print-at-home files that can be used with any deck of standard playing cards. These are currently available in English, Finnish, Swedish, Norwegian, and Northern Sámi. There is also a blank PDF for adapting cards to various issue areas, whether you choose to modify them digitally or print blank stickers to write on. Downloads are available at the project Zenodo page: zenodo.org/records/8334154

❄️ WELCOME ❄️

The first part of the workshop sets the context for participants, helping them feel more comfortable with the facilitators and each other. It can easily take 30 minutes. In general, it should include:

Adjustment Take stock of participants as they arrive. While some people may not show up, others may show up without having registered. Readjust table placements and name tags as necessary.

Orientation Review the workshop agenda and what to expect.

Purpose Explain the purpose and value of the workshop.

Permission Depending on the varying nature of projects, regions, funders, and participating groups, there may be specific forms or documents required for carrying out ethical research and data management. Prioritize these discussions and do the homework well in advance! Accordingly, inform participants of the policies around data collection, attribution/anonymity, photography, recording, file storage, and community access to research outcomes.

Intros Introduce the facilitators, chairs of each table, and note-takers. Introduce the ground rules, which emphasize open listening and understanding a diversity of perspectives. Finally, invite participants to introduce themselves to each other at their tables; allow ample time for this.

❄️ PART I ❄️

The Operational System

→ OVERVIEW

Using the game deck, participants will identify the most important aspects of the system in question (the example used throughout this guide is the reindeer husbandry system). With their chosen cards, they will create a “map” of the operational environment, using markers to draw connections and illustrate relationships between the elements involved.

It should take about 45 minutes for the map to be ready, meaning that elements are selected, arranged, and linked. It may be a slow start, but participants tend to understand and enjoy this part of the game.

→ OBJECTIVES

This part of the workshop establishes the operational environment of reindeer husbandry as it is now, setting the context for surprises and dreams.

Going through this process collaboratively ensures that there is a shared understanding among participants about the most important elements of the system and how they are related. It creates an environment where different views can be addressed early on, and a lively discussion can take place.

→ PLAY-BY-PLAY

1. **“First, let’s spread the cards out and take some time to read through them together.** Each card represents an element or topic related to reindeer husbandry.”
2. **“Taking turns, pick one card that you think represents the most important or central element in the reindeer husbandry operational environment.** I will mark each of these cards with the number 1.”

It is simpler for the table facilitator to mark each participant's chosen card with pre-prepared stickers.

Participants may provide justification for their choices, though this is not required. If there are elements that are not already included in the deck, participants can add elements by writing on the empty cards.

Participants should be encouraged to do this at any time during the workshop if they feel that an element is missing or unspecified.

3. "Taking turns, pick a second card that represents another important element. I will mark each of these cards with the number 2."

Depending on the group size, a third round may be necessary; at least 20 cards should be selected in total to build out a robust system. Allow time for participants to explain their choices, as these discussions can lead to important insights.

If participants still think there are important elements left in the deck, you may facilitate an additional round. Mark each card with the number that corresponds to each round. Again, the empty cards can be used to add missing elements.

4. "Remove the remaining cards and build a 'map' using the selected elements. Which cards are central? Which cards should be next to each other? Take time to group, move, and adjust the position of the cards."

There is no right or wrong way to make the map. Every group thinks differently; there may be arrangements like flow charts, clusters, radiating from a central point, etc.

5. "Once the cards are in position, draw the linkages between them. Using only one color of marker for this round, make any notes or illustrations that may help explain the relationships between elements and groupings."

It's fine to have disagreement about the importance of certain elements, arrangements, or connections.

The chair should mark these points of contention with a designated "conflict marker," such as a red arrow sticker. All views are acceptable in the discussion, but we want to acknowledge the areas of disagreement.

At the end of this activity, participants should take a break and move around the room to familiarize themselves with other groups' work.

❄️ PART II ❄️

Surprises and Preparedness

→ OVERVIEW

In this portion of the workshop, each group of participants will begin with the systems map they created in Part I and simulate the systemic response to a “surprise” card. How do global drivers or certain surprising developments impact the operational environment? How might communities cope, adapt, and prepare? It can take 30–60 minutes, depending on the emphasis of your workshop.

→ OBJECTIVES

An important aspect of future thinking is considering the effect of unexpected events and challenging developments. Responding to these simulated surprises can build a more robust understanding around cause and consequence within a livelihood.

→ PLAY-BY-PLAY

1. **“One person from our table, please approach the general facilitator and draw a Joker card. Once you return to our table, reveal what the card says.”**

Joker cards are prepared in advance, representing at least four different “surprises” such as Climate Change Effects, Climate Change Mitigation, Global Pandemic, and Geopolitical Tensions.

There should be enough for each table to draw at least one card for this portion of the workshop.

2. **“How does this surprise affect the operational environment we just built?** Let’s discuss which elements are impacted most, and whether there are secondary and tertiary effects. Use the second color of marker to draw new connections and notes. Feel free to add new cards where necessary.”

Allow for enough time and amendment before moving on to the next step. The group discussion will generate more insight than the map modification in isolation.

3. **“How can the community be better prepared for this kind of surprise? What factors would contribute to coping capacity and resilience? What types of tools and knowledge would allow for a strong, effective response?”**

If there's still time and willingness after this discussion about preparedness, another Joker may be drawn and steps 2 and 3 repeated. More specific “small Joker” surprise scenarios may also be used as prompts; examples relevant to reindeer husbandry might include an influx of refugees in the North, the end of meat consumption, an epidemic of reindeer disease, etc. It's also possible to discuss the cumulative effects of multiple surprises.

At the end of this activity, participants should take a break and move around the room to familiarize themselves with other groups' work.

❄️ PART III ❄️

Dreams and Futures

→ OVERVIEW

In this portion of the workshop, each participant reflects on their personal dreams related to the livelihood. Each group will share amongst themselves and discuss critical points on the operational map that correspond with their aspirations. A brief version can take about 30 minutes—or it could be considerably longer if the workshop’s emphasis is on desired futures.

→ OBJECTIVES

Dreams and aspirations weave a vision of desired future states of the current system. Meaningful change happens when there is a vision to strive toward; articulating these dreams can be both empowering for the individual and galvanizing for a community.

→ PLAY-BY-PLAY

1. **“Now we’ll talk about dreams and futures.** What are your hopes and aims as a practitioner of this livelihood? These can be generic or personal, as long as you’re willing to share it with us later. Write these down on your piece of paper.”

Participants should be given at least 5 minutes to reflect and write.

If time allows, include more specific prompts: What needs to change so that these aspirations are fulfilled? Who has the most power and responsibility to implement these changes?

2. **“Let’s discuss what’s necessary for those dreams to come true.** Which parts of the operational environment are involved? Everyone should place a sticker to mark a single critical element or connection on the operational map.”

Each participant should have a chance to respond aloud, describing their dream and explaining where they have placed their sticker. There will likely be comments and discussion between the whole group.

If time allows, continue with more discussion prompts: Is it possible for all of these different desired futures to co-exist? When there are contradictions and conflicts, how might they be addressed?

❄️ CLOSING ❄️

The general facilitator wraps up all group work and draws everyone's attention back to the entire room. This conclusion to the workshop may take about 30 minutes, and it should include:

Gratitude Thank everyone for their time and generous participation.

Insight Each participant and organizer should use a couple minutes to write down at least one insight gained from the workshop. These can be anonymous.

Feedback Invite all participants to give honest feedback. How did the process and discussion feel? Did it feel relevant, constructive, diverse? How would you develop or improve the methodology? With whom and where could this discussion be continued? Feedback can be raised immediately or written and delivered anonymously.

→ FOLLOW-UP

The organizing team should compile notes and photographs in a central location as soon as possible. It's useful to debrief and outline a report soon after the event while memory of the discussions and dynamics remain fresh.

Workshop participants should receive updates and follow-ups as promised at the beginning of the event.

Project organizers can communicate findings from the workshop to relevant parties, such as the scientific community, policymakers, and livelihood practitioners. Continue developing the workshop method, integrating feedback into the next event.

We feel this workshop requires some continuation, such as building upon Part III and working towards realizing stakeholders' dreams. The "when and how" discussion of next steps should be discussed among organizers and participants.